

SOCIOLOGICAL DEFINITION OF THE CONCEPT OF "SOCIAL CHANGES"

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Abstract. *This article provides a sociological definition of the concept of "social changes". In this regard, the types of social changes, social development of society, social changes in society, issues of social development were analyzed.*

Keywords: *changes, social changes, changes in society, social development, content changes, functional changes, structural changes.*

According to world scientists, the concept of "change" means the movement and interaction of objects and events, the transition from one state to another, the emergence of new characteristics, tasks and relations in them.

The concept of "social change" is used in sociology. In order to clarify this concept, it is necessary to know its social content.

First, the concept of "social change" is not widely used for us, but "social development" is widely used and has been used and developed in social sciences and applied sociology in our country for years. However, this concept is focused on development, improvement, and represents a certain type of change. However, there are many other changes that cannot be recognized as improvements. For example, emergence, growth, disappearance, transition, etc. These changes do not have a positive or negative meaning. They are not meant to progress or regress. The concept of "social change" covers a wide range of social changes, regardless of their focus.

Second, by "social change" any changes in society are not understood as change. They should be distinguished, that is, changes in any sphere of society are economic, political, spiritual, social changes. When we talk about social changes, we mean changes in social systems, social groups, social processes, social institutions, social organizations, their interaction, and relations.

When we approach social changes from a sociological point of view, T. Parsons' structural-functional analysis can be used.

He determined the following: 1) there are constant changes in the system; 2) changes in the system occur under the influence of internal and external factors. Social change is central to this model of tension, which creates an imbalance between social systems. Social tension fails to maintain the balance of relationships, which leads to the destruction of systems.

So, the concept of "social change" refers to the relations of social communities, groups, institutions, organizations with each other, as well as various changes that have happened to individuals over a certain period of time.

In other words, social change is a transfer from a social object to another social object, any change in the social organization of society, its social institutions and social structure, forms of behavior established in it. Such changes may occur at the level of interpersonal relationships (for example, changes in the structure and function of families); at the level of organizations and

institutions (education, science, constantly in terms of their content, organization); at the level of small and large social groups (the social composition of the population is changing); social and global scale (migration processes, economic and technological development of some countries, stagnation and crisis conditions of others, military threat, etc.).

4 types of social changes can be distinguished.

Changes in the composition of various social structures, for example, a small group, region, social stratum, nation, society, in general, changes in power structures, socio-cultural values, changes in family structure (large families, small families).

Changes affecting social processes. We follow the changes that occur in the field of social relations and relationships of different communities. In the course of these changes, there will be relations of harmony, conflict, equality, and subordination.

Changes in the functions of various social systems. They can be called social changes.

Changes in individual and collective activities or motivational social changes. Of course, the nature of needs, interests, motivations, behavior and activities may remain unchanged. Recently, it can be felt that people's income and personal income are affecting their behavior, thinking and mind.

These changes are closely related to each other. One kind of change must produce another kind of change. However, the interaction of social changes with cultural, economic changes is very complex. Changes in one area of society do not automatically lead to changes in other areas.

Social changes reflect changes in the state system, characteristics and relationships of social systems.

According to the structure and main characteristics of any system, the following changes can be distinguished:

Content (content) changes – system elements, their appearance or disappearance, changes in their properties. Since the elements of the social system are social subjects, for example, the change of employees of the organization, the introduction or cancellation of new positions, changes in positions or changes in the reasons for their activity, which can be reflected in increasing or decreasing labor productivity.

Structural changes - changes in the connection or structure of the structure of society. In a social system, it can look like a human action, for example. Also, people sometimes do not fully understand that structural changes are taking place in the team, it is difficult for many to fully accept that they were an ordinary employee yesterday, and today they are appointed as a leader.

Functional changes are changes in actions performed by the system. Changes in the functions of the system can lead to changes in its content and structure, in the surrounding social environment, that is, in the external relations of this system. For example, changes in the functions of state bodies may depend on demographic changes in the country and external influences, including external influences from other countries.

Development is a special type of change, and it is customary to talk about its existence. In the process of development, qualitatively, it is considered as a change that leads to the appearance of an object and is reversible. An evolving object looks self-contained at first glance, but a new set of features and connections takes this object into a completely new perspective. For example, individuals in any field of activity actually graduated from an educational institution in a different specialty, but they are evaluated and accepted differently by society because they occupy a completely different position in the social structure. Therefore, such people are said to have passed

the path of development. Change and development is one of the main aspects of the inclusion of all disciplines.

Changes are the interval between what the system was at a previous stage and what happened after a certain time.

Changes affect all living and non-living worlds of the world. Everything changes every minute. A person is born, grows up, grows old and dies. Everyone walks this path, old things disappear in society and new ones appear. In sociology, social change changes over time.

Factors leading to social change, such as changes in habitat, population dynamics and social structure, levels of conflict and competition for resources (especially in modern conditions), discoveries and inventions, culture formation (changing other cultural elements in interaction) .

The driving forces of social change are changes in the economic, political, social and spiritual spheres.

Social changes are one of the main topics of sociology of the 19th and 20th centuries, and O. Comte and G. Spencer conducted research in this regard.

The social theory of social change is divided into two main directions: social evolution and social revolution, which are considered the framework of the paradigm of social conflicts.

Social changes and its sociological definition

Society is never static. There are no unchanging objects and subjects in the social sphere. Interrelationships between people, cultural complexes, group composition also change. This, in turn, affects the politics of changes in society, the way of life of people. The ancient Greek philosopher Heraclitus (the end of the 6th century, the beginning of the 5th century BC) expressed his views that "Everything flows, everything changes", "You can fall into the flowing water once", that society is always changing. Changes happen every hour, every minute.

The study of changes taking place in society is divided into changes in social structures, social relations, and cultural changes in the culture of society.

Social changes can be seen in population growth, education growth, migration from rural to urban areas, changes in the environment, changes in the relationship between leaders and employees, the establishment of ministries instead of committees, etc.

Cultural changes can include inventions, changes in social norms, formation of new social values, cultural exhibitions, norms of behavior, etc. Sometimes, along with cultural changes, there can be social changes at the same time. For example, a change in moral standards leads to a change in social relations and vice versa. Almost all important changes have cultural and social aspects, so the term "socio-cultural changes" or short "social changes" is used.

In sociology, social changes refer to the changes that occurred in the structure of society, way of thinking, culture and social behavior. The transition of a social object from one state to another leads to significant changes in social organizations and social institutions.

There are many types of social change. They can cover the entire social system, sometimes be short-term or long-term, can lead to the development of the system or its decline. Social changes can be seen in the external environment, changes in the economy, ideological changes and other processes.

The concept of "social change" is not the same as the concept of "development". Material and spiritual objects show changes from simple to complex, from low to high, etc. The nature of social changes can be regressive, or it can be said that a certain social system and its main components, that is, a "change in balance".

What is the mechanism of social change, how do they work?

At the center of social change is copyright or accumulated innovation and change - innovation is called social innovation. Material innovations can form social innovations. As innovations permeate society, they bring about social change. However, not all proposed innovations may be accepted by the community. Some take it immediately, some take it for a long time. One of the factors influencing the resistance to innovation is the existence of subjective views in the society that prevent or even block the adoption of changes. For example, managers can pretend they cannot meet the demands of innovation, thereby blocking it.

A factor affecting the adoption of innovations is the demonstration of their capabilities to the general public. As innovation penetrates society, changes occur, but not all innovations are accepted by society. Social changes are not always supported, in such cases it is necessary to pay attention to subjective aspects. Experience shows that in order for the innovation to be adopted faster, its useful aspects should be demonstrated.

The peculiarity of social innovation is that it is difficult to have an immediate positive impact on society. Therefore, almost all social changes (for example, new laws) are implemented by overcoming mistrust, resistance, and often by coercion.

In the adoption of innovations, their compatibility with one or more cultures plays an important role. They are basically against existing cultural things. In such cases, the innovation is rejected by the society or accepted by its opposite sides, but these features occasionally cause protest, which does not ensure its stable acceptance. Then innovations are successful, that is, they combine cultural elements that have a positive social impact for society. Modern society is obliged to respond to innovations, to accept them in social, cultural and other spheres of human activity, to manage them. Indeed, social life brings innovation to a state of regression.

A society that is not in constant motion lags behind other news-seeking societies and cannot claim prosperity in social life.

Types of social change of society

Sociology divides changes in society into social, cultural, and political changes.

Social changes include shifts in the following social structures:

the emergence of new social groups, strata and classes;

the place and role of the "old layer" and their decrease in number;

changes in the field of social relations (communication and interactions, power relations, leadership in the emergence of multipartyism);

changes in the field of telecommunications (mobile communication , Internet);

changes in citizen activity (private entrepreneurship, every family is an entrepreneur).

Changes in the political sphere can be observed separately :

Changes in the Legislative Chamber and Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

activation of multi-stakeholderism;

ideological changes.

Cultural changes:

changes in the material and immaterial sphere (ideas, beliefs, skills, intellectual production);

changes in social norms: political, legal (old traditions, customs, adoption of new laws);

changes in the field of communication .

Social development of society

The problem of social changes is related to the concepts of "social development" and "social progress".

Social development means such a change of society in which new social relations, institutions, norms and values appear.

There are three characteristics of social development:
the process of gathering quantitative and qualitative changes;
goal orientation;
non-randomness of the change process.

It can be concluded from the above points that social development is such a direction of social development, in which it is focused from the lowest form to the top, from precision to more precision. In general, social development means social improvement of the society, improvement of the living conditions of the population.

Regression against social development is understood as the return of the society to the previous period of development level.

Progress as a global process refers to human action in all aspects of the development of society, and regression is a local process that studies individual parts of society in a short historical period.

In sociology, the following two important criteria are used to determine whether a certain society is developed: population welfare and production level.

Social changes in society

Social changes are changes that occur as an integral system in the activity of all components of society within a certain period of time. Among the main reasons for social changes, the following can be said:

Demographic changes (population growth, life expectancy, etc.).

Natural changes (floods, earthquakes, drought, depletion of mineral and energy resources, environmental pollution, increase in global air pressure, etc.).

Changes in technologies (automation of production, use of computer technologies).

Changes in the field of culture (scientific discoveries, beliefs and values).

Changes also occur as a result of the influence of various factors in society:

- a) population composition (ethnic composition, occupation and income);
- b) behavioral methods (changes in the level of social interaction);
- c) social structure (changes in the economy, power, family life, education and religion);
- g) culture (increasing the strength of any socio-political ideas).

Social changes include various changes in all spheres of society, shape the social dynamics and essence of society. Social dynamics can be expressed through the concepts of "social process", "social development", "social progress". Social dynamics includes taking into account the basic laws of social development. They include: the law of acceleration of history (each subsequent stage of the development of society requires less time than the previous one, which means the strengthening of the historical period) and the law of inequality (peoples and nations develop at unequal speeds).

Social change is a process that accumulates over a long period of time and causes irreversible changes, resulting in a qualitatively new state of the social object. The division of social changes into certain types can be done depending on the direction of ongoing changes.

Thus, progressive and regressive movement can be distinguished. Progressive (advanced) social changes mean the transition of a social system from a low level of development to a high level or a newly developed social system. Regressive social changes consist of a transition from a higher level to a lower level of social development. Between progressive and regressive changes there is not a relationship of opposites, but a kind of interdependence. Within the general progressive development of the social system, regressive changes of the individual may occur, on the one hand, while strengthening the regressive changes of the system, its individual components or functions may maintain and strengthen the progressive direction of development. Social development is possible, but this possibility does not mean its inevitability. Revival movement - upward and downward development is a progressive and regressive change.

Depending on the growth rate of social changes, the following types of development are distinguished: social progress and social revolution.

Social development is a gradual, step-by-step change in society. A *social revolution* is a rapid, radical change in society.

In society, various revolutionary changes occur in the forces of production, science and technology, consciousness and culture. Revolutionary changes include qualitative changes in social relations and the entire system. Human history is a gradual transition from one type of society to another. In the sociology of innovation, several types can be distinguished for different reasons. In world sociology, the concept of "modernization" describes the transition from industrial to post-industrial society. The concept of "modernization" is based on the concept of social development, it implies the matching of the cultural image of the countries to which period and in which region all societies belong, involvement in the scientific and technological process, but they are united by a system of universal human values.

Modernization is a process of changes, a set of economic, social, cultural, political changes that occur in society in connection with the adoption of scientific and technical achievements. Modernization is intended to show how countries can reach their current stage and solve their internal problems and enter the world community.

Based on the above considerations, two different types of modernization can be distinguished: organic and inorganic. Organic modernization implies that the entire stage of the previous evolution (for example, England) was prepared. Inorganic modernization allows the country to get closer to more developed countries and offer them access to advanced technologies, investment and experience (for example, Japan). When solving the issue of social dynamics in the process of modernization, of course, attention is focused on the "Global Strategy for Environmental Protection", and the main thing is that it is impossible to further develop society without preserving ecology. The main principles of sustainable development include the principle of biological anthropocentrism, the principle of reducing consumption by optimizing needs, the principle of environmental cleanliness of human activity, the principle of compensation, etc.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг “Социологик тадқиқотлар ўтказишни давлат томонидан қўллаб-қувватлаш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги 2019 йил 22 февралдаги ПФ-5667-сон Фармони // www.lex.uz
2. Бекмуродов М. Замонавий бошқарув социологиясининг долзарб масалалари. Монография.– Т.:Yoshlar nashriyoti uyi, 2020 йил.16,0 б.т.

3. Романов П.В. Социологические интерпретации менеджмента: исследования управления, контроля и организаций в современном обществе. – Саратов, 2000.
4. Социологическая энциклопедия. В 2 т. Т. 2. – М., 2003.
5. Содикова Ш. Ўзгаришлар социологияси. Ўқув қўлланма.- Т.: Akademiya, 2019 йил.